

DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS WITH THE HELP OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ART

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Abstract. *In this article, the traditions of the Uzbek people and their unique aspects - Uztoz - disciple tradition. Philosophical views of our scholars on the teacher-disciple traditions, — Uztoz-disciple manners and their structural foundations, personal qualities of the teacher, duties and duties of the student's manners, about the best qualities of a student, the etiquette of students' relationships with each other, the model of using the traditions of "Master-student etiquette" in education and training, in the education system and in the community*

Keywords: *teacher-disciple, philosophical view, disciple's manners, duties and responsibilities, personal virtue, generosity, courtesy, kindness, benevolence, openness, sweet treatment, patience, demandingness, chastity, obedience, contentment, correctness wickedness purity, gentleness, honesty, comradeship, friendship, cooperation, solidarity, loyalty, patriotism, humanitarianism, sincerity, neatness, cleanliness, intelligence, initiative.*

The spiritual foundations of the "Master - disciple" tradition in the process of teaching art. The traditions of the Uzbek people and their unique aspects are the Uztoz-disciple tradition.

Philosophical views of our scholars on the teacher-disciple tradition, — Uztoz-disciple etiquette and structural foundations, personal qualities of the teacher, duties and duties of the student etiquette, the best qualities of the student, the etiquette of the students' relationships with each other, in education and training A model of using the traditions of — teacher-disciple etiquette — in personnel training, in the education system and in the community.

"Personal qualities of a teacher"

Personal qualities of the teacher: generosity, kindness, benevolence, openness, sweet treatment, patience, demandingness, chastity, obedience, contentment, truthfulness, purity, gentleness, honesty, friendship, friendship, cooperation, solidarity, loyalty, patriotism, humanitarianism, sincerity, neatness, cleanliness, intelligence, initiative, honesty, honor, concern, respect for elders, respect for parents, kindness, etc.

"Professional qualities of a teacher"

Professional qualities of a teacher: the ability to teach students complex knowledge in an easy way (readability), to have specific knowledge of all types of trades and sciences, the ability to organize and manage students in a short time, concise and concise zero melodious, specific rhythm, image, frequency of speech, gaining reputation with his personal characteristics, knowledge, intelligence, strong will, being able to communicate and communicate, rationally imagining his future based on his human appearance, actions and deeds, the ability to direct faith and active life processes, the ability to inspire initiative, creativity, research, competence, i.e.,

interest in one's craft and the ability to teach it to young people from Siddi language, study in the field it includes leaving faithful disciples after him and others.

"Disciple's Etiquette"

Having a good attitude towards one's work, that is, loving one's profession;

Believing and believing in one's work;

Ability to maintain standards;

Paying respect to teachers;

To look away from all things that should not be seen;

Refrain from all unworthy deeds;

Not to deal with people who are against the teacher;

"The duties and responsibilities of the student before the teacher"

To be obedient to the teacher;

Continuing the traditions of the teacher;

Imitation of the teacher;

Patience - to be patient;

Be loyal to the teacher Be strong-willed;

Not to turn the teacher's face to the ground, but rather to raise his reputation;

Saying warm words in honor of the teacher;

Not to be friends with the teacher's enemies;

Respecting the teacher's family members;

Do not touch anything without the teacher's permission;

Do not look at someone else's things;

To treat the teacher with infinite respect.

"The best qualities of a disciple"

Thinking and speaking less in front of the teacher;

If you want to ask for advice, get permission from your teacher first;

Do not object when the teacher answers;

To be the first to greet the teacher when entering or seeing the teacher; Do not gossip about others;

Do not gossip about others in front of the teacher;

Complete observance of the etiquette of sitting and standing;

"Etiquette of students' relations with each other"

Being in a friendly relationship;

Being disciplined;

Don't tell others about someone's fault;

Not to be lazy and lazy;

Not betraying the deposit, not causing damage;

Not to be a hypocrite and hypocrite, not to be enmity, envy, gossip, incitement, not to tell lies;

Help each other;

Not to be indifferent;

Rejoicing at the success of a friend.

In the same way, **we will get acquainted with the schedule of organizing art classes based on pedagogical technologies.**

Topic:	M: Types of pattern elements and their uniqueness. Practice drawing pattern elements.
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EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY OF PRACTICAL TRAINING

Time - 4 hours	The number of students is 20-25
Form of training	Visual, practical performance
Practical training plan	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Types of pattern elements and their uniqueness. 2. Practice making simple pattern compositions with the participation of elements. 3. Practicing types of finishing patterns. 4. Learning how to draw an ink pen, targ'il, comb and obi.
<p>Purpose of training: To inform the students about the types of pattern elements and their uniqueness, to practice creating compositions from simple pattern elements, to practice the types of decoration of flower and leaf elements, to teach how to draw an ink pen, targ'il, comb and obi.</p> <p>Pedagogical tasks: - Explain the types of pattern elements and their uniqueness. - Practice making simple pattern compositions from elements. - Practicing types of finishing patterns. -Teaching how to draw an ink pen, targ'il, comb and obi.</p>	
<p>Pedagogical tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explain the types of pattern elements and their uniqueness. -Practice making simple pattern compositions from elements. - Practicing types of finishing patterns. -Teaching how to draw an ink pen, targ'il, comb and obi. 	<p>Results of educational activities: Student- Learns to make compositions from independent pattern elements;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learning to color and process the ground of the composition made of plant-like pattern elements.
Teaching method technique;	<p>Visual; Fish surface, Why</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — What diagram, —BBX table — Blitz survey technique
Teaching methods;	Educational methodical complex study manual, Educational methodical complex, video projector, handouts, demonstration posters
Form of education;	Team, group and pair work
Teaching conditions;	An auditorium equipped with computers and multimedia tools and a workshop equipped with equipment and materials.

TECHNOLOGICAL MAP OF PRACTICAL TRAINING

Stages time	Activity content	
	Teacher	A student
1 - Step Introduction (10 min)	1. The subject, its purpose, and the expected results of the training are announced.	1.1. He listens, writes, draws.

<p>2- Level Basic (60 min)</p>	<p>2.1. In order to attract the attention of students and to determine the level of knowledge, they are asked to prepare small sketches of questions and answers.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tell me the types of pattern elements and their characteristics? - Explain the ways of simple pattern compositions with the participation of elements? - Practicing types of pattern finishing. - To learn how to draw an ink pen, targil, comb and obi. <p>2.2. The teacher continues the practical training using visual materials.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teaching how to create pattern compositions on a free topic; - To teach the correct placement and composition of the selected pattern composition on the surface of the object, composition depending on the shape of the object. <p>Teaching how to create a pattern composite and choose colors, paint, and make-up.</p> <p>2.3. Emphasizes students to pay attention to their understanding of the main parts of the topic and draw them.</p>	<p>2.1. He hears. Explains the terms without repeating each other in turn. Self-made sketches are presented.</p> <p>2.2. Learn how to create pattern compositions.</p> <p>2.3. Learns to create a composition taking into account the placement of elements of painting in A3 format.</p>
<p>3- Stage Final (10 min)</p>	<p>3.1. It concludes the topic and draws students' attention to the main issue.</p> <p>3.2. Actively participating students are encouraged. Creating pattern composites independently is given as homework. Active students are assessed.</p>	<p>3.1. He listens, clarifies his thoughts.</p> <p>3.2. They record the assignment.</p>

VISUAL MATERIALS

This technology is used to solve controversial issues and conduct the educational process in a controversial way, because this technology allows students to defend their opinion, teaches free thinking and the ability to convey one's opinion to others, to openly debate and at the same time the culture of debate.

It helps the listeners to clearly and concisely express their thoughts on a simple piece of paper distributed to the audience, and to state supporting or counter-arguments.

The relationship between the art of painting and the types of applied folk art.

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